

BIM Implementation Guide: Challenges And Impacts in Organisations

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Abstract

Over the past years, Building Information Modelling (BIM) has emerged as a transformative tool for the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry, and it has entirely changed how projects are conceptualized, planned, and executed worldwide. The benefits of BIM projects are substantial, including reduced errors and omissions, better collaboration between all stakeholders, reduced rework, and reduced construction costs. Nevertheless, despite producing guides, standards, and other documents encouraging or promoting BIM implementation, several Organisations continue struggling to implement BIM in their operations. Given this, there appears to be a disparity between this methodology's theoretical benefits and its practical application, suggesting space for developing recommendations focused on overcoming the challenges reported by these Organisations.

This hypothesis motivated this research, which conducted a Focus Group discussion with seven experts (including professors, researchers, and practitioners) and interviewed eight BIM consultants and five organisation representatives who have undergone BIM implementation

processes. Aspects that this methodology has put forward are decision drivers, strategies to engage people, perceived benefits, perceived challenges, critical success factors, and impacts on the organisational structure. It has further validated a framework for BIM implementation, identifying specific phases and steps to organise knowledge about the process to provide a logical path for Organisations desiring to integrate BIM.

Between the main findings, this research points out that the research indicates that BIM adoption is now primarily influenced by market demands and government regulations, in contrast to 5 to 10 years ago when the focus was on innovation and gaining a competitive edge. Resistance to change emerges as the most significant barrier to implementation, highlighting the need for change management strategies. Technical issues and industry fragmentation also appear as relevant barriers and reduced knowledge of BIM still increases the effect of the rest of the difficulties. Implementing BIM leads to organisational structure changes, mainly in Human Resources, Marketing and Sales. Finally, the research points out the importance of applying a structured Strategic Planning and Change Management process.

Therefore, the main contribution of this research has been developing the foundation of a BIM Implementation Guide focused on the organisational context. Two of the most relevant developments presented within this guide foundations are a Maturity Assessment Matrix with a managerial focus and a Roadmap for strategic planning based on evaluating current processes. Other complementary developments that can be highlighted are: (1) a tool for assessing and selecting BIM software; (2) a proposal to define organisational BIM roles and responsibilities; (3) a tool for assessment of Risks related to BIM Implementation; (4) a selection of metrics and recommendations for the evaluation of implemented solutions; (5) Practical examples of processes, strategic statements, SWOT analysis applied to a BIM context.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/v1YvF-3hXbw>

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